

Keywords:

#EOOSMarketplace, #Biodiversity, #Ecology,
#GalaxyforEcology, #DataIntegration
#FAIRPrinciples

Galaxy for Ecology: Elevating FAIRness of Biodiversity Science Source Codes

Advancing Essential Biodiversity Variables via the European Galaxy Server

The Project Involved

Pôle National
de Données de Biodiversité

French Biodiversity e-infrastructure (PNDB) spearheads the Galaxy for Ecology movement, driving the transformation of ecology-focused source codes crucial in crafting biodiversity indicators. PNDB, in collaboration with the French museum of natural history and a consortium of 16 partners representing various French research institutes, universities, a biodiversity agency, and a French biodiversity foundation, champions this initiative.

The Challenge

Unlocking the FAIRisation of ecology-driven source codes presents a profound challenge. Biodiversity science wrestles with the complexity of integrating data due to the absence of a unified framework that harmonizes methods and information.

It's an intricate dance to gather interoperable data from diverse, raw, and scattered datasets, essential for comprehending the spatio-temporal dynamics of biodiversity across local and global scales.

The cornerstone lies in Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs), a pivotal framework for sourcing relevant data and constructing analytical workflows, from raw data to refined EBV data products.

Yvan Le Bras

Responsable de la coordination
scientifique et technique
infrastructure Pôle National des
Données de Biodiversité chez
Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle

"Our goal is to operationalize EBV concept to produce indicators by ensuring the highest levels of FAIRness for both data and source code implementation."

EOOSC service or tool used

To specifically achieve FAIRisation of source codes, we've harnessed the power of the European Galaxy server, usegalaxy.eu, propelling the creation of our Galaxy for Ecology initiative. Our partnership with the Freiburg University Galaxy team spans five years, dedicated to crafting Galaxy tools and comprehensive training materials.

Concurrently, we're refining and spotlighting our EBV operationalisation pilot for GEO BON, evolving and maturing its capabilities.

Explore the EOOSC resource here: [European Galaxy Server](https://usegalaxy.eu)

Useful tips & tricks

We saw the chance to make the most of established European Open Science services by launching an initiative focused on Ecology.

Discovering usegalaxy.eu was a game-changer, and the incredible assistance from the Freiburg University Galaxy team was instrumental in creating and effectively managing the Galaxy for Ecology initiative!

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The Research Community

Our research communities primarily focus on Biodiversity, spanning from genes to ecosystems and socio-ecosystems. While deeply rooted in Ecology, these domains also intersect significantly with Environmental and Earth Systems Sciences.

Benefits and impact

Our primary advantage lies in leveraging pre-existing shared services, circumventing infrastructure development costs and reaping benefits in terms of IT infrastructure and management.

This approach enables us to dedicate our efforts towards community-oriented tasks, contributing valuable tools, training materials, and user support to the shared system. Moreover, our participation in the collaborative Galaxy community empowers us to foster international initiatives, facilitating cross-country collaborations across Europe and worldwide.

This strategy significantly amplifies our impact not only on the components we're developing but also on the research articles we're involved in.

Why do I need EOSC?

Leveraging the EOSC European Galaxy server stood as the singular pathway to upscale and demonstrate the potential of FAIRizing source codes, particularly evident in their contributions to GEO BON. This global biodiversity observation network plays a pivotal role in shaping impactful management policies for global biodiversity and ecosystem services. Their approach advocates for the operationalization of Essential Biodiversity Variables through accessible and reproducible workflows.

The endorsement from EOSC acted as a catalyst, enabling their participation in numerous European project consortias and global initiatives like the Global Open Science Cloud and GO FAIR, fostering collaborations that transcend geographical boundaries and amplify their contributions to the realm of open science.

Useful material related to this story

Galaxy for Ecology

Across disciplines

In a previous role focused on life sciences and bioinformatics, they utilized the same European Galaxy server. Presently, they spearhead the Galaxy for Ecology initiative, paving the way for collaborations with colleagues involved in Galaxy for Climate. Through the FAIR EASE and EuroScienceGateway EOSC projects, they're actively broadening their scope to encompass all domains within earth systems, expanding the application and impact of their work across diverse scientific disciplines.

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